

CHARACTERISTICS OF SOCIALLY DESTRUCTIVE PROCESSES

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Abstract: The article discusses the content and main manifestations of social destruction. According to the author, social destruction manifests itself in a variety of factors aimed at absorbing the characteristics of the social sphere of society, violating its stability. Its main manifestations are associated with factors that degrade national identity, lead to a crisis in the institution of the family, disrupt the balance of interests of social groups and classes, deplete the potential of education, healthcare, social security systems, reduce the efficiency of cultural institutions, and reduce the level of everyday life of citizens.

Keywords: destruction, social destruction, social destruction, factors affecting national identity, factors leading to the crisis of the institution of the family, factors that disrupt the balance between the interests of social groups and classes, factors affecting the level of education, health care, social security systems, factors that reduce the effectiveness of cultural institutions, factors that reduce the standard of living of the population.

Every period of human history has its own ups and downs. The higher the level of progress and development, the more problems and destructive processes that hinder it will develop. Globalization, automation, and informatization, which are the specific trends of modern civilization, are manifested in every sphere of human society. While these trends serve the development of society, we are witnessing the formation of destructive processes that hinder development. All this can be expressed as a symbol of progressive and positive processes, development and creativity, of course. However, on the other hand, the last century went down in

history as a period of world wars and revolutions, geopolitical conflicts and coup d'états, conflicts and losses, social ills and tangled problems. In this regard, there is a need to study in detail the laws of destructive situations in the social sphere.

In the development of philosophical ideas, social destruction is understood as processes and factors, negativity and destructive situations that undermine stability in various spheres of society, divert it from development, lead to regression and decline. The emergence, formation and passing of social-destructive processes have a number of dialectical features. Socially destructive processes and situations can be manifested in various areas of society. In all areas, it occurs as a factor that erodes the main features of the system and undermines its stability. For example, economic destruction is associated with factors that erode and undermine the stability of the balance between productive forces and production relations.

Political destruction means discrediting of power, factors causing inertness of political parties, factors causing ineffectiveness of civil society institutions, lack of clear definition of strategic and tactical goals of political activity, disparity between political goals and methods and methods, factors and means of achieving them, successful political goals it is assumed that there is a shortage or lack of capacity of personnel capable of operating, that the norms of political law do not correspond to the needs and interests of society members. Spiritual destruction refers to the factors that disrupt the process of spiritual production, hinder the development of forms of social consciousness, and have a negative impact on social psychology and ideology. Social destruction is one such form of social destruction.

The social sphere of society also has a series of attributes. First of all, the social sphere of society in social philosophy refers to the set of historically formed relationships between people, social units such as groups and classes, ethnic units such as nation and people, and social institutions such as family. Each of its elements

and the nature of the relations between them changes over time under the influence of economic, political, spiritual and cultural factors.

In this regard, experts recognize the impact of economic factors on the social sphere. Spirkin, the means of production, the concepts of the economic sphere of the division of labor are important."

The main goal of the social sphere is to provide people with a decent lifestyle, to meet their needs related to housing, food, clothing, and health care, to bring the young generation to adulthood, and to form optimal relations between different groups and individuals. This goal is realized through the implementation of various social technologies.

Social technologies chosen in accordance with the purpose will not only provide the society members with a decent standard of living, expand the possibilities of full use of social services, but also create a basis for the establishment of social justice norms in the society.

Any factor that erodes the characteristics of the social sphere and undermines its stability is considered a socially destructive process. Destructive processes in the social sphere may be associated with:

a) factors that erode national identity; It is well known to us that there are characteristics that make a nation exist as a specific ethnic unit. The weakening or loss of these characteristics ultimately causes the nation to go down in history or to be absorbed into the composition of other nations. Therefore, it is necessary to note and prevent any factor that weakens national identity as the most dangerous destructive process;

b) factors leading to the crisis of the family institution; family has existed as the main social institution of society throughout the history of mankind. One of the central criteria of social development is related to the stability of the family institution and its well-being. Any destructive process that destroys the content and composition of the traditional family, impairs the functions and relationships of family members, ultimately causes the crisis of the entire society;

c) factors that disrupt the balance between the interests of social groups and classes; social cohesion requires ensuring harmony of needs and interests of different groups and classes; a breach in such harmony creates social anarchy, tyranny, a system based on the dictatorship of a particular group or class;

g) factors that undermine the potential of the educational system; "As the sages of the East said," the head of state said, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!" Therefore, any factor that serves to reduce the potential of the education system should be evaluated as a factor that weakens the value of intelligence and knowledge, and causes poverty;

d) factors that weaken the capacity of the healthcare system; population health and life expectancy are one of the important sources of social development. The health care system serves to ensure the stability of this factor. Any negative change in the system not only endangers the health of the population and shortens life expectancy, but also prevents the implementation of any significant social development program;

e) factors that worsen the social security of citizens; in a democratic society, a whole set of organizations capable of providing assistance to the elderly, citizens in need of social assistance, lonely people, temporarily unemployed for various reasons should operate. The factors that hinder the activities of these organizations

cause the erosion of the norms and principles of social justice, extinguish people's confidence in the future;

j) factors reducing the effectiveness of cultural institutions; the activity and function of these institutions must be proportional to the moral needs and interests of the population; the violation of this balance causes the spiritual needs of the members of society to be unsatisfied, as a result, the formation of the spiritual image of people slows down;

z) factors that lower the standard of living of citizens; standard of living is an important factor shaping the attitude of people to the social system; its decrease causes citizens' dissatisfaction with the social reality, threatens the stability of the society.

So, social destruction is manifested in various factors aimed at eroding the specific characteristics of the social sphere of the society and disrupting its stability. Its main manifestations are eroding national identity, leading to the crisis of the family institution, disrupting the balance between the interests of social groups and classes, eroding the potential of education, health care, and social security systems, reducing the effectiveness of the activities of cultural institutions, reducing the standard of living of citizens. is related to factors that reduce. In order to ensure the stable social development of the society, it is necessary to think carefully about the ways to eliminate these destructive situations.

References

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